

Oxidation Kinetics of Diethanolamine by Chloramine-T

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Kinetics of chloramine-T oxidation of diethanolamine in alkaline media has been investigated. The reaction is first-order both in amine and oxidant. The order in alkali is found to be nearly -1. The effect of varying the ionic strength on the rate of oxidation is negligible. It is proposed that the amine reacts in a slow step with *p*-toluenesulphochloramide to form an intermediate compound which subsequently interacts with another molecule of *p*-toluenesulphochloramide in a faster step yielding formaldehyde and other final products.

EXCEPTING the oxidation kinetics of diethanolamine by potassium persulphate¹ and potassium hexacyanoferrate(III)², little is known about the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of this substrate by other oxidants. The present paper reports the results of our kinetic investigations on the oxidation of diethanolamine in alkaline media. The main object has been to elucidate the reaction and mechanism and put forward a rate law consistent with the experimental data.

Experimental :

E. Merck (*Pro analysi*) sample of chloramine-T was used and the solution was stored in black coated bottle to prevent photo-chemical decomposition. The strength was determined using iodometric method³. All other chemicals used were either A.R. R. or extra pure quality and their solutions were prepared using doubly distilled water in pyrex vessels. The reaction vessels were coated with black varnish to exclude photo-chemical effects.

The requisite amounts of chloramine-T and sodium hydroxide solutions of desired concentrations were placed in a reaction vessel. This mixture and the amine solution of desired concentration were kept separately in a thermostated bath maintained at the desired temperature (± 0.1). The reaction was started by adding the requisite volume of the amine solution to the mixture. The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating the unconsumed chloramine-T iodometrically. Owing to the high initial concentration of the alkali, the pH remained constant during the reaction.

Results :

To determine the number of moles of chloramine-T consumed per mole of the amine, known amount of diethanolamine was mixed with ten to fifteen times its molar concentration of alkaline chloramine-T and the reaction mixture was left for five days at room temperature, when the reaction was complete. The unconsumed oxidant was determined.

It was found that the reaction can be represented by the equation :

The products formaldehyde and formic acid were confirmed by usual tests. The formation of formaldehyde in the oxidation of the same substrate by the other oxidants, such as periodate, HOCl and ClO₂ has also been reported.^{4,5} It has been examined qualitatively that formaldehyde is oxidised by chloramine-T, though the oxidation is very slow. From this it may be inferred that a part of the formaldehyde formed in the reaction is oxidised to formic acid.

The kinetic investigations were carried out at several initial concentrations of chloramine-T and amine at constant [OH⁻]. For each run a plot log a/(a-x) vs. time is straight line for nearly 60% of the reaction (Fig. 1). First order rate constants calculated

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log a/(a-x)$ vs. Time at 40°
[Chloramine-T] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [NaOH] = $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$
[Diethanolamine] $\times 10^3 M$ = 0.40(A), 0.50(B), 0.66(C), 0.80(D), 1.0(E), 1.25(F), 2.0(G)

ted from the equation $k = \frac{2.303}{t} \log a/(a-x)$ and also

from the plot, $\log a/(a-x)$ vs. time, agree closely with each other. The values of first order rate constants for a typical run at different temperatures are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

EFFECT OF CHANGE OF TEMPERATURE

[Chloramine-T] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [Diethanolamine] = $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$
[NaOH] = $4.0 \times 10^{-1} M$

Temp.	40°	45°	50°	55°	60°
$k \times 10^3$ (min. ⁻¹)	6.69	9.92	14.39	20.50	28.78

All subsequent investigations were also carried out with different concentrations of the amine, the other parameters being maintained constant. The rate constants, corresponding to different initial concentrations of the amine are summarised in Table 2.

TABLE 2

EFFECT OF VARYING [AMINE] ON THE RATE CONSTANT

[Chloramine-T] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [NaOH] = $4.0 \times 10^{-1} M$; Temp = 40°

[Amine] × 10 ³ M =	0.40	0.50	0.66	0.80	1.0	1.25	2.0
$k \times 10^3$ (min. ⁻¹)	2.88	3.30	4.90	6.00	6.69	8.0	13.70

The first order rate constants are proportional to the concentration of the substrate. The reaction is, therefore, of first order with respect to diethanolamine.

The reaction has been studied at seven initial concentrations of the oxidant and it has been found that the first order constants remain unaltered, confirming that the reaction is first order in the oxidant. Table 3 shows the constants at different concentrations of the oxidant.

TABLE 3

EFFECT OF VARYING [CHLORAMINE-T] ON THE RATE CONSTANT

[Diethanolamine] = $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$; [NaOH] = $4.0 \times 10^{-1} M$; Temp. = 40°

[Chloramine-T] × 10 ³ M	0.60	0.80	1.0	1.25	1.50	2.0	2.50
$k \times 10^3$ (min. ⁻¹)	6.54	6.93	6.69	6.93	7.33	6.93	7.02

The rate study measurements, made at several [OH⁻], exhibited a uniform decrease in the rate constant on increasing the [OH⁻] of the media. The order in OH⁻ ion is found to be nearly -1, as is evident from the following table.

TABLE 4

EFFECT OF VARYING [NaOH] ON THE RATE CONSTANT

[Chloramine-T] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; [Amine] = $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$; Temp. = 40°

[NaOH] × 10 ³ M	2.0	2.5	3.30	4.0	5.0	6.60
$k \times 10^3$ (min. ⁻¹)	13.4	10.28	8.59	6.69	5.53	3.98
$k \times [NaOH] \times 10^6$	2.68	2.57	2.83	2.67	2.76	2.25

Salts like, NaCl, KCl, CH₃COONa and K₂SO₄ are found to have negligible effect on the reaction rates.

The rates were also studied at different water-methanol mixtures. It is observed that an increase in methanol concentration slightly retards the rate of the reaction (e.g., $k = 6.69 \times 10^{-3}$ (min.⁻¹) at 0% methanol and $k = 4.328 \times 10^{-3}$ (min.⁻¹) at 25% methanol).

Arrhenius parameters were also calculated from the rate study measurements carried out at five different temperatures.

TABLE 5

ARRHENIUS PARAMETERS IN THE CHLORAMINE-T OXIDATION OF DIETHANOLAMINE

E _A (K cal/mole)	log A	ΔH* (K cal/mole)	ΔS* (e.u.)
14.64	6.267	14.02	-31.85

Discussion :

In aqueous solution, chloramine-T hydrolyses as follows :

The various oxidising species may be chloramine-T itself, *p*-toluenesulphochloramide and hypochlorite ion. As the rate is decreased on increasing [OH⁻], *p*-toluenesulphochloramide is undoubtedly the main oxidising species⁶.

It is proposed that the amine molecule reacts in a slow step with *p*-toluenesulphochloramide to form an intermediate compound which subsequently interacts with another molecule of *p*-toluenesulphochloramide in a fast step yielding formaldehyde. The steps thus involved are

Applying steady state treatment to the intermediates with the reasonable approximation that

$k'_{-1} \gg k'_2$ so that $k'_{-1} [\text{NaOH}] \gg 2k'_2 [\text{NH}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH})_2]$, the rate law is given by

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[\text{Chloramine-T}] = \frac{2k'_1 k'_2 [\text{Chloramine-T}][\text{NH}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH})_2]}{k'_{-1} [\text{NaOH}]} \quad \dots (7)$$

which is consistent with the experimental observations.

The deviation of order in alkali from -1 is explained by an insignificantly small fraction of the overall reaction to proceed via an intermediate path involving interaction of hypochlorite ion⁷ in steps (5) and (6). The rate law in this case is obtained as

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[\text{Chloramine-T}] = 2k'_2 [\text{Chloramine-T}] [\text{NH}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH})_2] \quad \dots (8)$$

showing the rate to be independent of $[\text{OH}^-]$.

A slight decrease in the rate constant on addition of methanol is in conformity with this alternative path.

The negative value of entropy of activation is explained by the proposed mechanism, e. g., the water molecule has been incorporated in the reaction sequence and this tends to decrease in entropy⁸.

Thus it may be concluded that chloraminometric oxidation of diethanolamine proceeds via two paths, one involving interaction of *p*-toluenesulphochloramide and the other of hypochlorite ion with diethanolamine in the rate determining step, the former being principally predominant.

According to the mechanism suggested, two moles of chloramine-T should be consumed for each mole of the amine, but the stoichiometric

investigations show that four moles of chloramine-T are consumed. Hence, it seems possible that half of the formaldehyde, formed in the reaction mixture, is oxidised into formic acid in the presence of excess of the oxidant.

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